

THE PROBLEM OF IDENTIFICATION OF A VACUUM DISTILLATION COLUMN**Aygun Safarova Agamirza***Associate professor,**Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Nigar İslamzade***Master,**Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University***Abstract**

Development of scientific bases of the automated control system allowing to increase economic efficiency of operation modes of vacuum block of oil refineries, which is one of the main technological processes of the fuel and energy complex, is an urgent problem of great national economic importance

In the presented paper the main technological parameters characterizing the vacuum column have been determined. A deterministic linear mathematical model capable of adequately reflecting the current technological state of the main apparatuses of the vacuum block of the technological complex of primary oil refining is developed. The adequacy of the obtained mathematical model has been checked and confirmed.

Keywords: oil refinery, K-4 column, regression equation, mathematical model, adequacy

Introduction

Among oil refining equipment, a vacuum unit is considered to be a complex technological system combining technological devices that differ in critical operating modes, both from the point of view of automation and control. Researches have shown that the main functions of vacuum units in modern technological systems of oil refining, carrying out primary oil processing, are obtaining from fuel oil used as a raw material the maximum amount of light and heavy oil fractions, providing standard quality indicators, with the minimum energy consumption.

The conducted studies have shown that the main devices of the vacuum block of the technological complex are:

- tubular furnace providing heating of fuel oil;
- vacuum boiler for fuel oil rectification;
- additional evaporative coolers.

It should be noted that the main apparatus of this unit by the degree of influence on obtaining the target products as a control object is boiler K-4, carrying out rectification of fuel oil under vacuum conditions. The main technological parameters characterising this apparatus are temperatures and residual pressure in different points - above and below the calorimeter, in the plates from which light and heavy oil and gasoil are extracted.

As a result of studying this device as a control object, it was found that the most disturbance factors are changes in consumption and quality indicators of raw materials - fuel oil, which enter the atmospheric unit for processing.

Analysis of scientific literature shows that the state of any complex technological system is characterised by limited information necessary to describe its current state at a given time. For this reason, the primary oil refinery can be considered as a deterministic or incompletely deterministic system, depending on the amount of a priori information characterising its current technological state.

When studying the vacuum unit as a control object in the primary oil refining technological complex of the oil production profile, it was concluded that one of the main difficulties arising in the development of a

complete mathematical model taking into account its specific features is the lack of ability to quickly measure the quality indicators of the product fractions obtained as a result of the technological process (for example, specific gravity of oil fractions, ignition temperature, kinematic viscosity, etc.). The evaluation of these parameters by means of laboratory analysis is very time-consuming, which makes it difficult to develop adequate mathematical models. On the other hand, the fact that the quality indicators of the fuel oil coming from the atmospheric block and used as a raw material in the vacuum block are not measured at all does not allow the transient processes and excitation factors occurring in the system to be taken into account in the mathematical models.

Taking into account all the above, a linear mathematical model was developed to describe its operation within the regulation limits, by studying the K-4 column, which is the main apparatus of the vacuum block of the primary oil refining technological complex, as a control object, and taking into account its specific characteristics, to build a complete mathematical model of this technological apparatus.

Solving of problem

Mathematical model is a symbolic representation reflecting functional mathematical dependencies of output and input parameters of objects.

The vacuum column K-4 is taken as the main apparatus for modelling in the vacuum block [1,2]. It is possible to build a mathematical symbolic model of this apparatus by means of passive experiments based on correlation and regression methods.

To build the model, first of all, statistical information is required. Collection of statistical information is possible by passive experimentation, since the investigated technological object has a risk of a number of accidents. Thus, if an active experiment is conducted at the object, the quality of the product obtained will change, the parameters will deviate from the regime values and it will be impossible to stabilise them [3,4].

When developing mathematical models, analytical and experimental modeling methods are used. Using these methods, it is possible to develop

mathematical models that allow studying all technological processes occurring in the system and the impacts on them. Experimental-statistical methods allow expressing mathematical dependencies between operating parameters that affect the course of technological processes in the form of both linear and nonlinear regression expressions. Using these dependencies, it is possible to determine the dependence of any two operating variables at any time, and it is also possible to study the processes occurring in all complex technological objects, regardless of their degree of complexity [5,6]. The specified methods are based on the processing of statistical information obtained as a result of passive experiments conducted at the object, using various software. In general, we can write linear regression models as follows:

$$Y = B_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k B_j X_j$$

Figure 1. Control object

As a result of the experiments, the following statistical data were obtained. The obtained data are shown in Table 1.

Based on the statistical data we have obtained, the constraint condition will be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 40 &\leq X_1 \leq 44 \\ 171.1 &\leq X_2 \leq 185.7 \\ 29.1 &\leq X_3 \leq 30.96 \\ 58.3 &\leq X_4 \leq 61.97 \end{aligned}$$

$$X_1 = [40.15 \ 41.23 \ 41.56 \ 40.39 \ 42.69 \ 42.4 \ 42.63 \ 42.5 \ 43.6 \ 43.56 \ 43.65 \ 43.89 \ 41.23 \ 42.56 \ 40.89 \ 40.1 \ 40 \ 41.2 \ 41.23 \ 41.65 \ 41.66 \ 41.65 \ 41.32 \ 41.9];$$

We enter the values according to the temperature of the fuel oil:

$$X_2 = [172.77 \ 174.5 \ 175 \ 177 \ 183.2 \ 185.1 \ 172.7 \ 172.3 \ 172.6 \ 173.1 \ 172.9 \ 183.5 \ 185.2 \ 182.2 \ 171.1 \ 174.56 \ 177.8 \ 179.5 \ 176.9 \ 185.7 \ 183.8 \ 180.2 \ 179.6 \ 178.2];$$

Fuel oil level ;

$$X_3 = [29.5 \ 29.6 \ 29.8 \ 29.1 \ 29.1 \ 29.7 \ 29.6 \ 29.3 \ 29.3 \ 29.2 \ 30.1 \ 30.2 \ 30.5 \ 30.5 \ 30.7 \ 30.1 \ 30 \ 29.8 \ 30.7 \ 30.8 \ 30.54 \ 30.12 \ 30.46 \ 30.66];$$

Fuel oil pressure ;

here B_i – unknown regression coefficients., X_i is input and Y_i is output.

The mathematical formulation of the modeling problem expressing the regression dependence between the vacuum section light oil product output (volume flow) and other parameters, and the sequence of solving the problem according to the formulation, are as follows [7].

Main technological parameters characterizing the vacuum column are follows:

- X1 — fuel oil consumption supplied to the K-4 column,
- X2 — fuel oil temperature in the column,
- X3 — level in the column,
- X4 — pressure at the top of the column,
- Y — light oil consumption

$$24.11 \leq Y \leq 26.19$$

Mathlab program is used to build a mathematical model of the object.

$$y = B_0 + B_1 X_1 + B_2 X_2 + B_3 X_3 + B_4 X_4$$

We enter the data getting from experiments into the program.

The fuel oil consumption values:

Table 1

Statistic data

N _o	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	Y
1	40.15	172.77	29.5	58.3	25.19
2	41.23	174.5	29.6	58.9	24.87
3	41.56	175	29.8	58.6	24.2
4	40.39	177	29.1	58.96	24.2
5	42.69	183.2	29.1	58.32	24.87
6	42.4	185.1	29.7	59.32	24.2
7	42.63	172.7	29.6	59.62	25.2
8	42.5	172.3	29.3	60.34	24.2
9	43.6	172.6	29.3	60.4	24.2
10	43.56	173.1	29.2	60.44	24.87
11	43.65	172.9	30.1	60.55	24.87
12	43.89	183.5	30.2	61.2	25.18
13	41.23	185.2	30.5	62.61	24.2
14	42.56	182.2	30.5	61.87	24.2
15	40.89	171.1	30.7	61.3	24.2
16	40.1	174.56	30.1	61.15	24.2
17	40	177.8	30	59.65	24.2
18	41.2	179.5	29.8	60.25	24.2
19	41.23	176.9	30.7	60.36	24.2
20	41.65	185.7	30.8	61.97	24.45
21	41.66	183.8	30.54	58.67	24.45
22	41.65	180.02	30.12	59.45	24.2
23	41.32	179.6	30.46	59.46	24.17
24	41.9	178.2	30.66	59.2	24.19

X₄=[58.3 58.9 58.6 58.96 58.32 59.32 59.62 60.34 60.4 60.44 60.55 61.2 62 61.87
61.3 61.15 59.65 60.25 60.36 61.97 58.67 59.45 59.46 59.2];

Light oil consumption;

Y=[25.19 24.87 24.2 34.2 34.87 34.2 35.2 34.2 34.2 34.87 34.87 34.2 34.2 34.2
34.2 34.2 34.2 34.2 34.2 34.45 34.45 34.2 34.17 34.19];

We include the number of experiments:

K=24

As a result of the calculations, the program calculates the coefficients of the equation:

$$B_0 = 61.4590$$

$$B_1 = 1.1740$$

$$B_2 = 0.2003$$

$$B_3 = -0.8598$$

$$B_4 = -1.1603$$

Substituting the coefficients into the regression equation, we obtain the following mathematical model:

$$Y = 61.4590 + 1.1740X_1 + 0.2003X_2 - 0.8598X_3 - 1.1603X_4$$

To ensure the adequacy of the mathematical model, it must meet certain criteria. This assessment is shown in Table 2.

Assessment of adequacy

Riyazi Modelin göstəriciləri		Analizdən alınan qiymətlər
1	Fisher criterion	3.9375
2	R squared	0.172415
3	Standard deviation	0.011492
4	Residual error	0.316329
5	Correlation coefficient	0.941523
6	Number of experiments	24

The results obtained confirm the adequacy of the mathematical model.

Conclusion

In the paper has been studied the main device of vacuum block-K-4 as control object in oil refinery facilities and the main mode parameters affecting the course of the process have been determined. During the study, it was established that the vacuum column (K-4) as a control object can be studied as a system determined or not fully determined depending on the volume of a priori information characterizing its current technological state.

The mathematical models of the main output coordinates of the K-4 column is developed using the regression analysis method and their adequacy is checked.

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